

ROCKET TO THE CLOUD – A FASTER WAY TO UPLOAD

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Synopsis

Rocket is the first attempt at handling one of the particular problems that other tools have failed to solve. This presentation will demonstrate AARNET's experiences and tools used high-speed data transfers of different kinds of research data.

Problem Scope

The research community in Australia is spread far and wide geographically, resulting in some cases to be physically far from one of our three CloudStor sites spread across the country. In addition, the data sets researchers store can be very varied, ranging from ephemeral data, to archival data. From many small files, to fewer very large files. This has meant that AARNET's software infrastructure needs to be spread in order to minimise network latencies between nodes, and this has created its own challenges in providing a reliable and reusable platforms for data sharing and transfer. Managing these requirements has resulted in more than one way to upload and share data.

Solution

CloudStor is a collection of open source products combined to aid researchers upload, share files to assist with research collaborations. The backend storage element is CERN's EOS, spread across three sites across the country. The frontend elements are:

- ownCloud
- FileSender
- Minio
- Rocket

ownCloud is the main interface to CloudStor. It provides an easy to use GUI and allows users to drag and drop files. It also offers a useful synchronisation client similar to Dropbox and Microsoft OneDrive. It also provides a webdav gateway into user storage.

FileSender is for ephemeral data. Users can share files with others and solves the problem of emailing large files to other researchers. With the recent development work done for v2, users can upload multiple files at once with data rates of around 700MB/s from a standard business grade laptop. FileSender also allows our users to take advantage of end to end encryption, parallel thread uploads and an API for automated transfers.

Minio is an interface into CloudStor that allows users to connect existing software they use into our storage via an Amazon style S3 connector. This helps integrate directly into a research's storage allocation within CloudStor without needing to modify the users' software or workflows.

Rocket helps some users run scientific instrumentation and require a tool to quickly upload vast amounts of datasets quickly. Usually the ownCloud sync client is used but for some it is not quick enough because it uploads files one by one with a single thread via the ownCloud webdav gateway, which can choke when presented many little files. In addition, the sync client is geared more to synchronisation rather than just upload, meaning that both client and server store the same data. This is undesired by instrument users as it causes issues and interrupts the natural workflow. In some cases the instrument PC's disk becomes full of synchronised data they do not need. For this reason, we have developed a

product called Rocket, which integrates directly into ownCloud and EOS.

Rocket is an upload only tool that bundles and uploads payloads of data into CloudStor using parallel threads. A payload can consist of:

- Bundles small files
- Chunks of large files

Settings such as payload sizes, number of threads, maximum number of files per payload, payloads to buffer in memory is all user modifiable. This means users can fine tune settings to best utilise their local network and PCs.

By keeping payload sizes consistent and by using parallel threads, in the right conditions, we are able to upload data as fast as the PC can read off the local disk. Rocket uploads files into our ownCloud, so it is possible to upload into a shared space and have files arrive at a group of users as files are uploaded.

How it works

Rocket is split into two major parts, a frontend and a backend. The frontend is a Windows application that lets the user adjust settings and to start transfers.

Once a transfer starts, ie the user clicks Push, Rocket begins to scan the directory specified and creates payloads of a user-defined size. Once a payload is created, it is sent to Rocket's backend via a https web call. Payloads are sent as soon as they are made up to a user-defined limit. As the number of concurrent uploads are limited/set by the user, it is possible to read of the disk faster than upload. Because of this Rocket can buffer payloads in to memory limited/set by the user.

The backend is a combination of haproxy, apache, php-fpm, php7, xroot and EOS, as seen below.

When a payload reaches the backend, it is broken up into files or file chunks depending on its type and reassembled on EOS via the xroot API. Xroot is used because it allows us to interact with EOS directly thus bypassing ownCloud's webdav gateway (used by the ownCloud sync client). This allows us to ignore EOS checksum checks on partial files and only generate a checksum once the file is uploaded, this increases file IO dramatically in EOS when uploading large files. In order to keep our server load low we have deployed 10 servers per that are load balanced by our haproxy nodes.

Once a transfer has completed the Rocket frontend sends a signal to ownCloud to update the metadata caches for new and updated files, allowing users to see the files in their home directory or in a shared directory.

Results

In our tests, we were able to achieve speeds of over 6 GB/s from an un-tuned standard PC with a 10 Gb Ethernet and cheap SSD. In this example, we were reaching the limits of the SSD and the amount of memory in the PC.

CloudStor Speeds (megabits/s)

It is unfair to simply compare numbers of each product as each is designed to serve a different purpose for a different set of requirements. Given bandwidth, Rocket does perform reasonably well, with room for improvement.

Summary

AARNET is in the unique position to do its best to help serve researchers with uploading and sharing data over its network. Simply running ownCloud and giving users access to cloud storage is no longer enough. We identified that additional ingress methods, such as FileSender, S3 via Minio, and Rocket, were required to meet the needs of the user communities. As an NREN we have to support more products, services and code bases, with the outcome of users being able to use, interact, and collaborate in a way that was simply not possible for them in the past.